

THERMAL EXPOSURE EFFECTS ON THE STRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SHORT-FIBRE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of isothermal exposure and elevated test temperatures on the structure and the mechanical properties of magnesium matrix composites containing Saffil-fibres and unreinforced alloys was investigated. Samples of different alloys such as CP-Mg, AZ91 and QE22 were subjected to temperatures up to 300 °C for 1, 10, 100 and 1000 hours. At low temperatures the unreinforced samples became weaker by the heat treatment, while the composites did not show a marked degradation in the mechanical properties. With increasing treatment temperature a degradation could be observed depending on the matrix alloy.

Keywords: Magnesium alloys, Composites, Thermal stability, Mechanical properties, High temperature properties, Interface reactions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The low density of magnesium alloys (1,7 g/cm³) is often counteracted by insufficient mechanical properties which prevents an exploitation of the weight-saving potential. Fibre reinforcement however, can improve the yield strength and the tensile strength at both ambient and at elevated temperatures as well as improve the Youngs modulus /1/. The density increases only slightly. Suitable reinforcing components are Al₂O₃-short fibres which exhibit a good property profile and a high availability /2/. The composites can be produced economically by squeeze casting /1/. Since magnesium possesses a high affinity to oxygen, the melt reacts with the fibre during the production process which results in a good bonding /3/. Further reactions are possible during heat treatment and application at elevated temperatures. Isothermal annealings were performed to determine the extent to which reactions occur under operating conditions. Modifications in the structure and mechanical properties were investigated and correlated.

2. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

In the present investigation commercially pure magnesium (CP-Mg), the casting alloy AZ 91 and creep resistant alloy QE 22 were employed. The composition of the alloys is given in Table I. Saffil fibres from the company ICI were used as reinforcing components. The fibres consist of 96 - 97% δ -Al₂O₃ with a low share of α -Al₂O₃ and of 3 - 4% of SiO₂. The SiO₂ serves to stabilize the δ -phase

and the grain size of the fibres. The fibres are available as preforms with a planar isotropic fibre orientation and with different fibre contents.

Table 1. Chemical composition of employed alloys.

Alloying element	AZ 91	QE 22
Al	8.5 - 9.5 %	-
Zn	0.4 - 0.9 %	-
Ag	-	3.0 %
Rare Earth	-	2.3 %
Zr	-	0.4 %
Mg	balance	balance

For the present investigation, both unreinforced and reinforced samples were produced by squeeze casting. The preforms having a fibre volume content of 20%, were infiltrated vertically to the orientation plane of the fibres. The alloys subsequently underwent a standard T6-heat treatment, in order to achieve an approximately equal initial state for the residual stresses, CP-Mg was also subjected to a heat treatment. The parameters employed for the alloys are listed in table 2.

Table 2. Heat-treatment parameters for the unreinforced alloys and the composites.

Alloy	Solution treatment	Ageing
CP-Mg	520 °C/ 5,5 h/ water	200 °C/ 8 h
AZ 91	415 °C/ 18 h/ air	168 °C/ 16 h
QE 22	520 °C/ 5,5 h/ water	200 °C/ 8 h

The unreinforced alloys and the composites were annealed isothermally in air for 1, 10, 100, and 1000 hours. The annealing temperature was 150 °C and 200 °C for CP-Mg and 300 °C for AZ 91 and QE 22. Subsequently metallographical and electron microscopical investigations were performed on the samples and tensile tests were carried out at ambient temperature as well as at 150 °C and 200 °C.

3. EFFECT OF THERMAL EXPOSURE

Prolonged annealing results in structural and property modifications in the unreinforced alloys as well as in the composites. In addition to the precipitation and coagulation processes caused by aging, fibre/matrix-interface reactions could occur in the composites which on the one hand affect the bonding and on the other hand could result in a damage to the fibres and thus in a decrease of the strength.

3.1. CP-Mg

Prolonged annealing heals the lattice distortions in both the unreinforced samples and in the composites. The number of twin boundaries decreases. Simultaneously, the MgO-particles, which occur as a reaction product between fibre and matrix, increase as a function of the annealing temperature. Figure 1 depicts the interface after the heat treatment and an annealing time of 100 h at 200 °C.

Figure 1. SEM-photographs of the reaction products at the surface of the fibre a) after heat treatment b) after isothermal annealing of 100 h at 200 °C.

The strength of the composite and the non reinforced alloy was determined at both ambient and elevated temperatures (Figures 2 and 3). Isothermal annealing causes a decrease in the strength of both composite and alloy, although both cases reveal that even after long annealing times, the composite is clearly superior to the unreinforced alloy. Whereas the annealing temperature has only a slight effect on the decrease in strength of the unreinforced alloy, its effect on the composite is more pronounced. The strength of the reinforced alloy after an annealing time of 1000 hours at 150 °C is still 180 MPa, whereas after prolonged annealing treatment at 200 °C it has fallen to 125 MPa.

The results of the tensile tests at elevated temperatures lie below those of the ambient values. Furthermore, the strength decreases with increasing annealing time, albeit to a lesser extent compared with the tensile tests performed at ambient temperature. The reason for this is a decrease in the matrix yield strength and consequently, at higher temperatures, the sharp-edged reaction products no longer act as inner notches to the same extent as at ambient temperature. Simultaneously, the decrease in the matrix yield strength with increasing temperature results in a drop in the critical fibre content, whereby the reinforcement effect increases /4/.

Figure 2. Strength of unreinforced and Saffil-fibre-reinforced CP-Mg at ambient temperature and at 150 °C as a function of annealing time at 150 °C.

Figure 3. Strength of unreinforced and Saffil-fibre reinforced CP-Mg at ambient temperature and at 200 °C as a function of annealing time at 200 °C.

3.2 AZ 91

The structure of the casting alloy AZ 91 consists in the heat-treated state of α -crystalline solid solution with areas of $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ precipitated in lamellar form. Massive areas of $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$, as found in the cast state, occur only sporadically. For the composites, the intermetallic phase prefers to precipitate in the area of the fibres (Figure 4a). Prolonged annealing leads to the formation of both discontinuously precipitated and massive areas of $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ (Figure 4b). In addition, MgO and $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$, which occur at the fibre/matrix-interface grow with increasing annealing time. The reaction products are sharp-edged (Figure 4c), as observed in CP-Mg.

The effect of a prolonged isothermal annealing on the mechanical properties at ambient temperature and at 200 °C is illustrated in Figure 5. After heat-treatment, the strength of the composite is insignificantly higher than the strength of the unreinforced material. The effect of annealing at 300 °C on the strength corresponds to the results of previous investigations performed at 200 °C /5/. After an annealing time of 1 hour the strength decreases distinctly to then rise once more up to an annealing time of 100 hours. This is attributed to the augmented formation of reaction products at the fibre/matrix-interface which improve the bonding. Increasing growth, however, damages the fibres which, as a result of their sharp-edged form, act as inner notches. This negative effect is observed after an annealing time of 1000 hours. This results in a decrease in strength so that the strength of the composite lies below that of unreinforced alloy. The results of the high temperature tensile tests also reveal that the composite is not superior to the unreinforced alloy. At elevated temperatures, the effect of the sharp-edged reaction products on the strength is not as great as during the tensile tests performed at ambient temperature. The tensile strength at elevated temperatures remains constant after 100 hours.

Figure 4. Structure of the fibre-reinforced alloy AZ 91 a) after the heat treatment b) after isothermal annealing 300 °C/1000 h c) reaction products at the surface of the fibre after an annealing time of 1000 h at 300 °C.

Figure 5. Tensile strength of reinforced and unreinforced alloy AZ 91 at ambient temperature and at 200 °C after isothermal annealing at 300 °C.

3.3 QE 22

The structure of the creep resistant alloy QE 22 after heat treatment comprises massive precipitations of type $Mg(Ag)_{12}RE$ which prefer to form on unreinforced alloy at the grain boundary and between the fibres for composites. During an isothermal annealing these precipitations initially increase as a function of the annealing time, and later decrease again. Unlike CP-Mg and AZ 91, there was no marked increase in the reaction products which were identified in a previous investigation as Al_2Nd and Mg-Ag-rare earth oxide [5].

The modifications in the structure have an effect on the mechanical properties, as is illustrated in Figure 7. The strength of the unreinforced alloy is reduced above an annealing time of 10 h at 300 °C. this applies to the tensile strength at both ambient and at elevated temperatures. For the composite, the increase in the intermetallic phase affects a drop in the strength which rises again with the dissolving of the precipitations. The brittle intermetallic phase results in a weaker load transfer into the fibres. Over a prolonged annealing, the strength of the composite also decreases, the values, however, are higher than those for the unreinforced alloy. In particular for the tensile strength at elevated temperatures is the effect of fibre reinforcement positive.

Figure 6. Structure of the fibre reinforced alloy QE 22 a) after heat treatment b) after an isothermal exposure of 1000 hours at 300 °C c) SEM-photograph of the fibre surface after an annealing time of 1000 h at 300 °C.

Figure 7. Tensile strength of the unreinforced and fibre-reinforced alloy QE 22 at ambient temperature and at 200 °C.

4. CONCLUSIONS

To determine the thermal stability of composites, prolonged isothermal annealing tests were performed on different fibre-reinforced magnesium alloys and on the unreinforced alloys. The modifications in the structure and in the mechanical properties were determined by tensile tests at ambient temperature and at 150 °C and 200 °C.

(1) The composite with CP-Mg proved superior to the unreinforced alloy in its strength at ambient temperature as well as at elevated temperature. At both investigated annealing temperatures, increasing annealing time results in a loss of strength, which is, however, more pronounced at the higher temperature. This is caused by the increase in the MgO-reaction products which improve bonding but also damage the fibres which as a result of their form act as inner notches.

(2) AZ 91 is unsuitable as matrix material in Saffil-fibre composites. The strength of the reinforced alloy at ambient and elevated temperatures lies, in the heat treated state and also after prolonged annealings, in the range of the unreinforced alloy. An isothermal annealing affects an increase in the reaction products at the fibre/matrix-interface so that after an annealing time of 1000 hours, the fibres have been damaged and the ambient strength falls to below that of the unreinforced alloy.

(3) After prolonged annealing at 300 °C the Saffil-fibre-reinforced alloy QE 22 and the unreinforced alloy experience a decrease in strength at both ambient temperature and at 200 °C. However, even after an annealing time of 1000 hours, the composite is superior to the unreinforced alloy. This effect is noticeable in particular during tensile tests at elevated temperatures.

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